

ISLAMIC BANKING IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA: REGULATORY CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Islamic finance has been becoming mainstream worldwide for its ethical and risk-sharing approach. However, conventional legal frameworks and regulatory requirements set operational limits that make Islamic finance a big challenge in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The paper will present an overview of challenges and regulatory barriers to using profit-sharing contracts such as those of Mudarabah and Musharakah. It also calls for legal changes, educational efforts, and capacity-building in the banking sector to increase awareness and the market share of Islamic finance products. The article compares the practices of conventional banking with the principles of Islamic finance, suggesting ways that could be conducive to increasing the market size for Islamic finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The growth of Shariah-compliant financial products needs to expand in the region to cope with the increasing demand for Shariah-compliant financial products and services.

Keywords: Banking, Islamic banking, regulation, profit-sharing

INTRODUCTION

Islamic finance is guided by the principles of Islamic law, which prohibits interest (riba), uncertainty (gharar), and investments in businesses associated with haram activities, like alcohol, gambling, or pork-related industries. There are more principles of Islamic finance, but these are the most important. Islamic finance is the operational form of the Islamic moral economy, whose ultimate goal is reintegrating human well-being and social justice (Avdukic et al., 2021). Instead, it emphasizes profit sharing, risk sharing, asset-backed financing, and ethical investments. The two most popular contracts in Islamic economics theory are Mudarabah and Musharakah. Mudarabah is based on profit-sharing and implies that one party gives out the capital and the other gives expertise, with the profits shared between them. Musharakah involves a joint venture in which all parties put in the capital and the knowledge and share both the risks and rewards (Ayub, 2007). The other key (and more widely used) contracts are Ijarah and Murabaha, which take the overall schema of Islamic financial products to new horizons. These models represent highly flexible Sharia-compliant solutions for

meeting financing needs, although they are similar to some conventional financing structures. These models aim to achieve justice, transparency, and shared prosperity, ensuring fairness and equitability in all forms of financial transactions.

In Bosnia and Herzegovina, a country with a significant Muslim population (around 50%), there has been an increasing demand for financial products and services that adhere to Islamic principles (World Bank, 2016). This has been fueled by personal and business needs, as individuals and enterprises in the country increasingly require funding consistent with their religious beliefs (Dusuki & Abdullah, 2007). The global expansion of Islamic finance has contributed to spreading awareness of and familiarity with Islamic financial instruments in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Unfortunately, though, the existing legal environment in the country contains significant barriers to the complete establishment of Islamic finance rules. For example, classic legal laws require the disclosure of interest rates or fixed returns, to which implementing contracts like Mudarabah or Musharakah by Islamic banks becomes impossible since these contracts are based on the sharing of profits and not predetermined returns. This proves that, with the increasing global demand for Islamic finance, there is an immediate need for an Islamic financial supporting infrastructure that can meet the increasing demand and also conform to local legal regulations. Research in this direction has proved that a flexible operational and structural platform is required for growth, as it will offer immense support to customers, banking operations, and risk management processes.

The primary aim of this article is to reflect on the difficulties that hinder the realization of Islamic finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Despite an apparent demand for it, various regulatory, legal, and operational obstacles put a cap on its substantial realization of Islamic finance principles (Meskovic et al., 2024). These limitations involve restrictive legal environments, problems related to models of profit-sharing and trade, and mobilizing funding by Islamic law. This article will, therefore, take the identification of the problems one step further to investigate possible solutions and prospects of Islamic finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This article will attempt to understand possible ways of overcoming such barriers via studies of potential legal reforms, regulatory adjustments, and educational initiatives. The article will also examine the potential for growth in the Islamic finance industry, considering the dynamism in the global environment and the growing interest in ethical and Shari‘ah-compliant financial products.

The central research question of this study is whether existing legal and regulatory frameworks in Bosnia and Herzegovina hinder the implementation of Islamic finance and whether potential legal reforms could facilitate the adoption of Shariah-compliant financial products. that the existing regulatory framework-the original design for conventional banking presents significant barriers to applying the principles of Islamic finance.

Reforms that would introduce profit-sharing contracts, such as Mudarabah and Musharakah, will enable Bosnia and Herzegovina to offer an inclusive banking

system in order to cope with increasingly growing demand for Shariah-compliant financial solutions, increased awareness by the general public, and professional training in Islamic finance.

OVERVIEW OF ISLAMIC FINANCE PRINCIPLES

The most important principle of the Islamic financial system is the prohibition of *riba*, a term covering all forms of interest. According to the Shariah law, interest-based lending for income is unfair and exploitative because it represents an unearned burden on the borrower and does not share the risks of the transaction with the lender (El-Gamal, 2006). Instead, Islamic finance advocates contracts under which the profit is shared between the lender and the borrower; therefore, the participants share the attached risks and returns. This ensures that transactions are fair in sharing profits and losses (Ayub, 2007). The emphasis on mutual benefits eliminates the potential for exploitation, and thus, a more just economic system is encouraged, which is the fundamental purpose of finance under Shariah guidance.

Islamic finance places a significant emphasis on sharing risk and profits, ensuring that both parties to a financial transaction share the possible loss and profit. In Islamic finance theory, such financing models are mostly implemented through two main contract structures: *Mudarabah* and *Musharakah*.

Mudarabah is a profit-sharing partnership in which one party provides the capital (*rab-ul-mal*) while the other contributes expertise and management (*mudarib*). The distribution of profits and losses is pre-determined. However, losses are to be borne only by the financier except if the losses are the manager's fault or are because of negligence or misconduct. This contract structure encourages entrepreneurship because the manager can carry out a project without direct financial risk but is an active participant, whereas the capital provider benefits from any financial success of the venture (Meskovic et al., 2024).

Musharakah is a contract in which all partners contribute capital and share profits and losses in proportion to their respective investments. This, in turn, makes *Musharakah* conducive to cooperation by aligning the interests of all partners. The risks and rewards under *Musharakah* are shared based on a fair profit-or-loss-sharing ratio. The model is especially preferred in long-term projects where the sharing of risks is indispensable for mutual benefit (Ahmed, 2011).

Islamic finance ensures that all transactions are backed by tangible assets or services, which means the various financial activities are strictly linked to the real economy. This important principle aims to mitigate speculative activities and gain financial stability by basing transactions on the real economy (Ayub, 2007), ensuring more stable and sustainable economic model.

Murabaha is one of the cost-plus financing modes in which a bank purchases an asset and resells it to a client at a markup with the payment deferred. The markup, which

defines the bank's profit margin, is disclosed at the time of the contract, reducing opacity and cutting ambiguity in the deal. Since the cost and the profit margin are both exposed, this transaction complies with Islamic rules, which do not allow interest (*riba*) and ambiguity (*gharar*). *Murabaha* is the most widespread instrument of Islamic finance. Its simplicity and compliance with Shariah law make it particularly popular among Muslims today.

Ijara depicts an arrangement in which the bank buys an asset and then rents the same to a customer for a specified period. This means that the ownership of the asset lies with the bank, but the client is allowed to use it in one form or another for rent payment. According to the contract terms, at the end of the lease, the user can obtain ownership of the asset. *Ijara* complies with Islamic financing principles in that it prohibits payments of interest and ensures that real, tangible assets back each financial transaction. In simple words, this structure provides an effective tool for carrying out financial activities related to purchasing high-value assets like real estate or machinery.

Comparative Overview

Islamic banking differs from conventional banking in several key aspects:

- **Interest vs. Profit-sharing:** Conventional banks primarily earn income by charging interest on loans (*riba*), while Islamic banks generate profits through profit-sharing, leasing, and asset-backed sales. This fundamental difference ensures that Islamic banks focus on risk-sharing, where both parties share the risks and rewards, rather than risk-transfer, where the borrower bears the entire burden (El-Gamal, 2006).
- **Ethical investments:** Islamic banks are prohibited from investing in businesses involved in activities considered haram, such as gambling, alcohol, and pork production. In contrast, conventional banks have no such restrictions, allowing them to invest in a broader range of industries, including those not compliant with Islamic principles (Ayub, 2007).
- **Asset-backed transactions:** Islamic finance requires all financial transactions to be backed by tangible assets or services, ensuring that financial activities are closely tied to the real economy. This approach reduces speculation (*gharar*) and promotes stability. Conventional banking allows for more speculative and unsecured financial activities, where not all transactions are necessarily tied to tangible assets (Ahmed, 2011).

METHODOLOGY

This research is conducted qualitatively to understand the obstacles faced by Islamic banks in Bosnia and Herzegovina at the regulatory and operational levels. This methodology is structured around a literature review of the regulatory framework for

the banking industry in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Each of these methods has been designed to investigate contemporary barriers to implementing Shariah-compliant financial products and to foster the growth of Islamic finance within the region.

An extensive literature review was conducted to study the principles of Islamic finance, the regulatory regime in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and current operating challenges within Bosnia and Herzegovina. The study involved the examination of academic papers, legal documents, and financial regulators' reports to understand global Islamic finance practices and the issues about Bosnia and Herzegovina. The critical resources gathered were the academic articles about Islamic finance, together with its financing models, and documents that stipulated the banking law of Bosnia and Herzegovina in the context of the Law on Banks (2017) and the Law on the Protection of Consumers of Financial Services. The review was an integral baseline for understanding the primary barriers in the legal and regulatory framework, which restrict the full implementation of Islamic finance within Bosnia and Herzegovina.

This research adopts a case study approach toward Bosnia Bank International (BBI), the only Islamic bank in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The paper contains a case study on BBI's operational framework to understand how it tries to operate under the principles of Islamic finance while being bound by conventional banking regulations.

LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK OF ISLAMIC FINANCE IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

The normative legal framework for banking in Bosnia and Herzegovina has been designed to support financial stability, transparency, and safeguarding of consumers. The central part of that framework is the Law on Banks, which regulates the establishment, operation, and regulation of the most essential standards of capital adequacy, risk management, and corporate governance of banks. The law also defines the responsibilities of the Banking Agency of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina in monitoring and enforcing these regulations to ensure that the sector maintains its integrity.

Islamic finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina has particular challenges in its regulation under the present system. The existing laws do not explicitly support Sharia-compliant financial products, which do not allow the creation and application of profit-sharing contracts and trade-based models, specifically *Mudarabah* and *Musharakah*. The fact of the matter is that it is difficult to implement any of these and face the challenge because only one bank in the country offers Islamic banking, and it is classified as a traditional bank under the name of BBI that has to operate under similar legal and regulatory requirements.

As Efendić (2011) noticed, BBI is less efficient than its conventional counterparts, mainly in terms of cost efficiency, which is relatively low due to the absence of regulatory accommodations for Islamic banking. For example, BBI's cost efficiency was measured at a mere 46%, pointing to the necessity of retooling regulations to support Islamic financial products better.

This also manifests another challenge to issuing Islamic financing products whose principles prohibit interest (*riba*) in that it is a requirement that interest rates on loans, as well as returns on deposits, be absolutely stated. The existing legal framework is principally based on the regulation of conventional banking, according to Kozarević et al. (2014), and thereby indirectly forms a barrier to Islamic banks. For this reason, the legal framework restricts these banks from issuing the full line of wholly Shariah products. This includes limitations associated with the application of risk-sharing contracts, such as *Mudarabah* and *Musharakah*, which are fundamental to Islamic finance but challenging to operationalize in Bosnia and Herzegovina due to the lack of a specialized legal environment for the implementation of the said contracts.

Another weakness that befalls Islamic banks is their inability to establish risk management policies tailored to their needs, which makes their activities even more cumbersome under the existing conventional banking system.

The existing legal framework in Bosnia and Herzegovina imposes significant restrictions on profit-sharing contracts, such as *Mudarabah* and *Musharakah*, which are central to Islamic finance. These contracts rely on flexible regulatory treatment that allows for profit and loss sharing without predetermined interest rates. However, current regulations mandate that clients must be informed in advance of the exact amounts they will be charged or receive, conflicting with the variable nature of profit-sharing agreements. As Efendić (2011) points out, Bosnia Bank International struggles with offering these Shariah-compliant contracts under the existing regulatory framework, as it is required to function under the same legal rules as conventional banks. This creates significant challenges in implementing true profit-sharing mechanisms, which inherently involve variable returns.

The most important law for banking business in Bosnia and Herzegovina is the Law on Banks (2017). Article 2 (Definition of Terms) mentions all terms used in the law have the following meanings. Regarding the definition of bank, deposit, and a loan, it says the following:

„a) A bank is a joint-stock company with headquarters in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (hereinafter: the Federation), which has a license to operate from the Banking Agency of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (hereinafter: the Agency), whose activities include receiving deposits and funds with the obligation to repay and granting loans for its own account, and may also perform other activities in accordance with this law.“

The definition in this law refers to a traditional, conventional banking structure where banks operate under interest-based transactions (loans and deposits), which is not permissible in Islamic banking. The idea of accepting deposits with the obligation to repay with interest is prohibited under Shariah law because it involves *riba* (usury or interest). For Islamic banks, the activities of receiving deposits and providing financing must be compliant with Shariah principles. Islamic banks operate without interest and instead use profit-sharing or other Shariah-compliant modes of financing (such as *Murabaha*, *Mudarabah*, or *Ijarah*). Thus, Islamic banks need to adapt this

legal framework to ensure that their operations align with Islamic laws, even though the framework described is designed for conventional banks.

“ee) A deposit is considered a cash deposit based on a contract concluded with the bank where the bank commits to accept, and the depositor commits to place a certain amount of money with the bank. By this contract, the bank acquires the right to manage the deposited funds and is obligated to return them under the conditions specified in the contract.”

Islamic banks accept deposits under the principle of *qard* (interest-free loan) or as *Mudarabah* (profit-sharing). In *qard*, the bank guarantees the repayment of the deposit, while in *mudarabah*, the depositor shares in the profit or loss of the bank's investments. The key difference from conventional banking is that Islamic banks cannot promise a guaranteed return or interest, only a share in the profit.

“ff) A loan is considered a contract by which the bank commits to making available to the borrower a certain amount of money, for a fixed or indefinite time, for a specific purpose or without a defined purpose, and the borrower commits to pay the agreed interest to the bank and return the received amount of money at the time and in the manner determined by the contract.”

The loan definition here involves the bank lending a sum of money to a borrower, who agrees to pay interest and repay the principal according to the contract terms. This type of contract is based on *riba*, which is prohibited in Islamic law. Islamic banks do not provide interest-bearing loans. Instead, they offer financing products such as *Murabaha* (cost-plus financing), where the bank buys a product and sells it to the customer at a markup, or *ijarah* (leasing), where the bank leases an asset to the customer. The profit for the bank is derived from the sale or lease, not from charging interest on a loan. Therefore, the conventional definition of a loan is incompatible with Islamic finance, which prohibits interest and instead promotes trade-based, profit-and-loss sharing arrangements.

Another important law relevant to Islamic banks in this market is the Law on the Protection of Consumers of Financial Services. Article 15: Providing Information to Consumers in the Negotiation Phase, says:

„Banks, microcredit organizations, and leasing providers are obliged to provide the consumer with information about the terms and all significant characteristics of the service they offer in the form of a standard information sheet on a representative example of the service in written or electronic form, which relates to contracts on monetary deposits/loans/microloans/leasing, authorized overdrafts, or the opening and management of accounts, as well as contracts for the issuance and use of payment cards (hereinafter referred to as the offer) in a way that will allow the consumer to compare offers from different providers of the same services and assess whether the contract meets their needs and financial situation, but which at no time will mislead the consumer.

The information sheet referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article should contain 5) The amount and variability of the nominal interest rate, 6) The effective interest rate, and the total amount that the consumer must pay or that must be paid to them, 7) The amount and number of loan installments and the periods in which they are due (monthly, quarterly, etc.), 11) The interest rate applied in the event of a delay in fulfilling obligations and the rules for its adjustment, as well as other fees payable in the event of non-fulfillment of obligations.“

The first issue in this law is the interest (*riba*). The mention of nominal interest rates (point 5) and effective interest rates (point 6) conflicts with the core principles of Islamic finance. As mentioned before, Islamic financial institutions do not charge interest on loans. Instead, they utilize profit-sharing, leasing (*Ijarah*), trade-based (*Murabaha*), or partnership (*Musharaka*, *Mudharaba*) contracts where profit is derived from legitimate trade or investment activities, not interest. Therefore, in an Islamic finance context, the information sheet would instead provide details about the profit rates, rental payments (for *Ijarah*), or the profit-sharing mechanism (for *Musharaka*/*Mudharaba*) rather than interest rates.

Islamic finance emphasizes the importance of transparency and the need to provide all material information to ensure fairness and clarity in financial contracts. The requirement to provide detailed information about the financial product (such as the total cost, payment schedules, etc.) aligns well with the Islamic finance principle of full disclosure (*Tawheed*) and avoiding *gharar* (excessive uncertainty). This article's mandate for comparing different offers and ensuring that the consumer is not misled supports the ethical principles in Islamic finance that prioritize the well-being of the consumer and fairness in financial dealings.

Point 11 refers to the interest rate applied in case of delayed payments and the rules for its adjustment, which is problematic in Islamic finance. In Shariah-compliant contracts, while late payment penalties are discouraged, institutions may charge a fee to cover administrative costs or encourage prompt payment. However, this fee cannot be considered as income or profit for the institution. In Islamic finance, a common practice is for any penalties collected from late payments to be directed toward charitable purposes in order to avoid any benefit from *riba*. Alternatively, banks may use other non-interest-based mechanisms, such as late payment compensations based on actual costs incurred rather than interest.

Therefore, while the requirement to provide transparent and comparable information about financial products aligns well with Islamic finance values, the references to interest-based elements, such as nominal and effective interest rates and late payment penalties, are incompatible with Shariah-compliant finance. Islamic financial institutions would replace these elements with Shariah-approved alternatives like profit-sharing, rental rates, or fixed profit margins, ensuring that all transactions comply with Islamic ethical principles.

Trade-based financing models like *Murabaha* and *Ijara*, which are essential components of Islamic finance, also face regulatory hurdles in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The legal requirement for transparency and the prohibition of disguised

interest complicates the implementation of these models within the conventional banking framework. According to Efendic and Meskovic (2012), Islamic banks such as BBI face challenges in offering Shariah-compliant financing because of the restrictive legal environment. The law on banks does not permit trading, which means that Islamic banks cannot use *Murabaha*, *Salaam*, or *Istisna*'s contracts.

The legal requirement for clear disclosure of costs and returns presents one of the main regulatory obstacles for Islamic finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Conventional banking rules specify that banks give customers exact information on predicted returns and interest rates. This runs counter to the Islamic finance concept of risk-sharing, in which actual business performance must determine returns since guarantees of them are impossible. While keeping Shariah compliance, Meskovic et al. (2024) observe that any Islamic bank would struggle to meet these disclosure standards. Further complicating their activities, Islamic financial institutions must find a balance between the requirement for openness and the basic Islamic premise that returns are uncertain and depend on the success of the underlying commercial activity.

PRACTICAL CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTATION

Using Islamic contracts such *Mudarabah* and *Musharakah* inside Bosnia and Herzegovina's current legal system presents great difficulties. Similar challenges were noted in a 2013 Serbian market research by Bećirović & Dudić. The Law on Banks outlines particular criteria on openness, pre-defined charges, and interest disclosure that cannot be mixed with the flexible and profit-sharing character of Islamic finance arrangements. Efendić (2011) notes that these limitations make it practically impossible for the sole pure Islamic bank in the nation, Bosnia Bank International, to completely implement Shariah-compliant financing arrangements. BBI has to run within the same legal framework as traditional banks, hence it is challenging to match the profit-sharing ideas fundamental to agreements like *Mudarabah* and *Musharakah*.

Lack of sufficient knowledge and experience in Islamic finance among bank staff members presents still another significant obstacle. Most bankers in Bosnia and Herzegovina may not completely grasp the ideas and operations of Islamic finance as most of them are taught traditional banking techniques. Concerned also by Kozarević et al. (2014), who emphasize the requirement of capacity building in Islamic finance risk management, this knowledge gap impedes the efficient promotion and implementation of Islamic financial products. Like Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kammer et al. (2015) underline that the lack of technical knowledge in Islamic finance generally restricts the sector's development, especially in emerging nations.

Many consumers in Bosnia and Herzegovina also lack knowledge about Islamic financial ideas and products. This ignorance could cause misunderstandings and resistance to applying Islamic financial services. Increasing acceptance and demand depends on educating clients on the advantages and practices of Islamic financing. While Meskovic (2022) emphasizes that BBI Bank has placed major effort into public education till 2022, Solo et al. (2020) underline even more how public education on

Islamic banking is necessary to address these difficulties and improve client acceptance.

Clients often have expectations based on conventional banking practices, such as fixed interest rates and guaranteed returns. These expectations do not align with the risk-sharing and variable return principles of Islamic finance. As noted by Amine (2016), this misalignment is common across regions where Islamic finance is being implemented, as clients often expect Islamic products to behave similarly to conventional ones (Amine, 2016). Bridging this gap requires significant effort to educate clients and align their expectations with the unique aspects of Islamic financial products.

On the other hand, we must emphasize that BBI is a champion in the implementation of subsidized financing lines in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Zogić et al (2024) note that the bank has implemented many financing lines and helped physical and legal persons to expand their capacities and overcome financial obstacles related to liquidity. Although based on the conventional banking model, these lines often offer a 0% rate for the customer.

POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Changing current laws and rules to fit Sharia-compliant financial products will help Bosnia and Herzegovina's Islamic finance adoption go more smoothly. This covers trade-based ideas like Murabaha and Ijara as well as changing the Law on Banks to let profit-sharing agreements like Mudarabah and Musharakah exist. Particularly in relation to interest and predefined returns, these revisions would need to change transparency and disclosure criteria to fit Islamic financial values. Efendić (2011) argues that since the present regulatory system drives Islamic banks to operate under conventional banking rules, legal reform is absolutely necessary for allowing BBI to deploy the whole spectrum of Islamic financial products. Furthermore, implementing particular laws for Islamic banking, in line with models elsewhere, would offer a clear legal framework encouraging the expansion of the industry. Belouafi and Belabes (2010) contend that allowing the particular requirements of Islamic finance in a traditional system depends on a flexible regulatory environment.

Successful application of Islamic finance depends on investments in the training and growth of bank staff members. This entails thorough courses on operating techniques, Islamic financial ideas, goods, and concepts. Lack of knowledge in Islamic banking among professionals presents a major obstacle for Bosnia and Herzegovina, therefore restricting the efficient management and promotion of Sharia-compliant financial products. Focused education programs will help bank staff members to better manage and advocate Islamic financial services, therefore enhancing their knowledge and abilities. Kammer et al. (2015) stress even more the need for capacity development in Islamic finance in order to close the knowledge disparity globally. Improving education among potential consumers about Islamic finance can help to increase demand and acceptance of it. This can be achieved via targeted awareness campaigns, educational seminars, and informational pamphlets stressing the benefits and workings of Islamic financial products. A fundamental barrier in Bosnia and

Herzegovina, as Meskovic (2022) points out, is the broad ignorance of Islamic financial concepts among the people. This knowledge discrepancy could lead to misinterpretation and opposition to dealing with Islamic banks. He emphasizes even more the need for public education.

Creating innovative Islamic financial solutions assists banks or other companies to meet the several wants of customers. These could include fresh profit-sharing schemas, investment products, and finance choices compliant with Shariah guidelines yet satisfying the specific requirements of the market. Expanding Islamic banking in emerging nations depends on creativity, as Amine (2016) notes since tailored solutions are needed to meet local demand and regulatory constraints. Islamic banks in Bosnia can diversify their offerings and attract more customers by means of new instruments like Sukuk or Shariah-compliant investment vehicles.

Restructuring current financial products to eliminate interest and ensure they are underpinned by actual assets allows them to suit Islamic values. For example, Murabaha agreements—cost-plus financing—may be created from conventional loans; leasing items can be altered to fit Ijara patterns. Emphasizing its flexibility for the local market, Lojo-Bajrić and Hadžić (2020) investigate the possibility of using declining Musharakah for home financing in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This approach would enable Islamic banks to offer a wider range of compliant financial products, therefore maintaining their competitiveness while adhering to Shariah rules.

FUTURE PROSPECTS AND OPPORTUNITIES

Given Bosnia and Herzegovina's high Muslim population and growing demand for Shariah-compliant financial products, Hadzic et al. (2012) find that Islamic finance has tremendous market potential in this part of the world. As more people and companies learn to know Islamic financing, this will rise. In the financial industry, the untapped market presents great potential for expansion. Trokić (2016) claims that if diaspora remittances were tested using Shariah-compliant vehicles like the Islamic Bosnian Diaspora Mutual Fund, the sum would rise dramatically and significantly help the national economy. This Islamic mutual fund pools remittances for SMEs in Bosnia; so, fresh financial sector growth prospects are within reach. Based on rent based on the market, Lojo-Bajrić and Hadžić (2020) stated that Islamic financial institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina have more room for maneuvering and there is the prospect of larger applicability.

If we want society to benefit from these institutions, it is essential to work on introducing and implementing laws that support the development and operation of Islamic financial institutions. This includes creating a clear regulatory framework for Shariah-compliant products. Regulatory bodies should look to develop specific regulations that address the unique needs of Islamic finance, such as accommodating profit-sharing models and asset-backed financing (Kammer et al., 2015). A dedicated framework will provide stability and encourage Islamic financial institutions to grow (Kammer et al., 2015).

Countries like Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, and the UAE have integrated Islamic finance into their conventional banking systems by developing regulatory frameworks that allow the accommodation of Shariah-compliant financial products. For instance, the Islamic Financial Services Act 2013 in Malaysia provides a clear regulatory framework for the functioning of Islamic banks side by side with conventional banks under Islamic principles. These models can be replicated by Bosnia and Herzegovina merely through regulatory reforms that will serve the needs of both conventional and Islamic finance. With the establishment of a dual banking system where Islamic banks can operate under dissimilar sets of rules in line with Shariah, Bosnia, and Herzegovina would be able to successfully manage the surge in Islamic finance without necessarily compromising financial stability. Malaysia is the country with the most developed Islamic financial system, and this is not a coincidence. Meskovic et al. (2023) proved that regulation plays the most important role in financial system development.

The Malaysian Islamic Financial Services Act 2013 thus puts into law separate jurisdiction for said Islamic banks to operate businesses alongside conventional banks. Similarly, in the United Kingdom, special provisions were introduced through the Financial Services and Markets Act 2000 (Regulated Activities) Order to accommodate alternative finance investment bonds or Sukuk as one way of opening its jurisdiction to Shariah-compliant financial transactions. It can initiate a dual banking mechanism whereby Islamic banks are operating under different regulatory policies that have been designed to meet certain principles. Also, the amendment of existing legislation, such as the Law on the Protection of Consumers of Financial Services, which dictates fixed-rate disclosure of interest, should be amended in the direction of allowing the disclosure of profit rates or rental receipts, as is already being done by countries such as the United Arab Emirates, whose central bank has issued extensive Shariah-compliant regulations supporting Murabaha, Ijara, and other Islamic instruments. These examples can help in establishing a more flexible banking environment in Bosnia, more inclusive and friendly, in order to meet the increasing demand for Islamic financial products.

Developing and implementing educational programs for both bank employees and potential clients is critical for enhancing understanding and acceptance of Islamic finance principles. Providing specialized training to bank employees will ensure they are well-versed in Sharia-compliant products, helping bridge the current knowledge gap. For clients, awareness campaigns should explain the benefits and unique features of Islamic finance to foster trust and increase demand.

Encouraging the development of innovative Islamic financial products tailored to meet the needs of the local market will help Islamic banks remain competitive with conventional banks. Amine (2016) emphasizes the importance of creating new financial instruments that align with Shariah principles while addressing the specific requirements of clients in Bosnia (Amine, 2016). This could include developing products for home financing, investment funds, and SME financing that cater to Bosnia and Herzegovina's unique market needs.

Public awareness campaigns about the benefits and operations of Islamic finance create trust and confidence in the minds of potential clients. Meskovic (2022) further stresses that focused marketing campaigns have to be created to better inform the general public about the stability and resilience of Islamic financial products, which were more resistant to shocks during the global financial crisis.

For instance, targeted educational campaigns on awareness can be issued adopting Malaysia's campaigns where national awareness programs play a critical role in raising the knowledge of Islamic finance among the general public. Finally, international collaborations with institutions involved in Islamic finance, for example, IsDB, will lead Bosnia in capacity building in Islamic finance through training and development programs that raise awareness among employees and clients alike. These actions would spell out the pragmatic, actionable way ahead for Bosnia and Herzegovina in creating an enabling environment where Islamic finance can flourish.

IMPLICATIONS

Recommendations for the policymakers and financial institutions from this article are valuable not only for Bosnia and Herzegovina but also for other countries with similar environments. Legal and regulatory reforms proposed can provide a clear roadmap for the appropriate integration of Islamic finance into the national financial system. Bosnia and Herzegovina would do well by moving toward and embracing the dual banking system. Such a system in which Shariah-compliant products exist alongside conventional banking seems appropriate for a country like this with a 50% Muslim population. Hopefully, this would lead to a better regulatory environment, more foreign investments, and increased economic growth. Looking at countries like Malaysia and the UAE, this model increases not only financial inclusion but can also contribute to financial stability.

Important insights into capacity building and public awareness are raised in the article. Given the nature of financial institutions, especially BBI, there should be intensive training of internal staff and its clients about Islamic finance products. Staff retention programs are crucial, however. This would lead to improved product design and customer satisfaction, and Islamic finance would take over the market share in Bosnia and Herzegovina. In turn, institutions that introduce Islamic financial solutions will find themselves well-positioned to capitalize on a growing demand for ethical and Sharia-compliant options.

The Bosnian case has wider implications for the Islamic finance industry. It shows a number of challenges countries with conventional legislation are likely to face when trying to accommodate Islamic finance. These findings also inform similar efforts in other regions, based on a framework for legal reform, public education, and capacity building. Successful implementation of Islamic finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina could open new opportunities for regional cooperation. Also, integration with global

Islamic finance markets is possible, further enhancing the country's financial resilience and diversification.

CONCLUSION

Barriers to introducing Islamic finance in full capacity in Bosnia and Herzegovina are complex. They include restrictions in existing legal frameworks, a lack of proper expertise amongst bank employees, and limited client awareness. These limitations require regulatory reforms as remedies, together with capacity building through training and awareness campaigns and innovative Islamic financial product designs. Overcoming these challenges will be crucial for the further development of Islamic finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina. By providing a favorable regulatory environment, enhancing the knowledge and skills of banking professionals, and creating awareness among clients, the potential of Islamic finance can be realized in practice.

These solutions require the collaboration of all stakeholders. Such collaboration includes regulatory body (Federal Banking Agency) as well as financial institutions and community leaders. Together they can create a more inclusive and diversified financial sector. Such a sector can further support Bosnia and Herzegovina's economic growth and social welfare.

Removing regulatory barriers would add long-term value to the financial system and the economy of Bosnia and Herzegovina. In reforming the legal framework of Bosnia and Herzegovina to make accommodations for Sharia-compliant financial products, there is potential for attracting foreign investments from Islamic countries. Another very important area is that of inclusive financial products, which would widen access for Muslims and ethical investors. A strong Islamic finance sector would enhance economic resilience through risk-sharing and asset-backed financing. This promotes financial stability. Addressing these challenges could position Bosnia as a regional hub for Islamic finance, driving sustainable growth and financial inclusion.

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